

Supplementary Information 1: Figure, Tables and Contigs.

Distribution of the top 5001 Blast Hits on 5000 subject sequences

Supp. Fig. 1. BLAST result of BtPa-BetaCoV/GD2013 (accession KJ473820.1) against SRR5885860.

select all 100 sequences selected

GenBank Graphics Distance tree of results

Description	Common Name	Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E value	Per. Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Bat coronavirus HKU5-2, complete genome	Bat coronavirus HKU...	42566	42566	100%	0.0	91.91%	30488	EF065510.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Bat coronavirus HKU5-5, complete genome	Bat coronavirus HKU...	42560	42560	100%	0.0	91.91%	30487	EF065512.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Bat coronavirus HKU5-3, complete genome	Bat coronavirus HKU...	42538	42538	100%	0.0	91.89%	30488	EF065511.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5, complete genome	Pipistrellus bat coron...	42424	42424	100%	0.0	91.83%	30482	NC_009020.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pipistrellus abramus bat coronavirus HKU5-related isolate BY140568, complete genome	Pipistrellus abramus ...	42418	42418	100%	0.0	91.82%	30511	MN611520.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> BtPa-BetaCoV/GD2013, complete genome	BtPa-BetaCoV/GD2013	42359	42359	100%	0.0	91.79%	30480	KJ473820.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5 isolate BY140535, complete genome	Pipistrellus bat coron...	42267	42267	100%	0.0	91.73%	30494	MH002340.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5 isolate BY140562, complete genome	Pipistrellus bat coron...	42021	42021	100%	0.0	91.59%	30480	MH002341.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5 isolate YD13403, complete genome	Pipistrellus bat coron...	27429	42621	100%	0.0	91.67%	30529	MH002342.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Bat coronavirus HKU4-4, complete genome	Bat coronavirus HKU...	9609	11181	56%	0.0	78.49%	30316	EF065508.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tytonycteris bat coronavirus HKU4, complete genome	Tytonycteris bat coron...	9603	11170	56%	0.0	78.48%	30286	NC_009019.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Bat coronavirus HKU4-3, complete genome	Bat coronavirus HKU...	9598	11164	56%	0.0	78.47%	30286	EF065507.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Bat coronavirus HKU4-2, complete genome	Bat coronavirus HKU...	9598	11164	56%	0.0	78.47%	30286	EF065506.1

Supp. Fig. 2. BLAST analysis of the novel HKU5-related Merbecovirus against the NCBI nr/nt database.

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Query ID: lcl|Query_57217

Description: lcl|NovelMerbecovirus

Molecule type: dna

Query Length: 387

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GenBank Graphics Distance tree of results

Description	Common Name	Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E value	Per. Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Bat coronavirus isolate_16BF221 RNA-dependent RNA polymerase gene, partial cds	Bat coronavirus	654	654	99%	0.0	97.40%	392	KY432470.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Bat coronavirus isolate_16BF244 RNA-dependent RNA polymerase gene, partial cds	Bat coronavirus	649	649	99%	0.0	97.14%	392	KY432471.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Bat coronavirus isolate_16BF104 RNA-dependent RNA polymerase gene, partial cds	Bat coronavirus	649	649	99%	0.0	97.14%	392	KY432468.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Bat coronavirus (BtCoV/A1206/2005) RNA-dependent RNA polymerase gene, partial cds	Bat coronavirus...	649	649	99%	0.0	97.14%	445	DQ648802.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5 PREDICT-EHA-156-12-NL13856 RNA-dependent RNA polymerase mRNA...	Pipistrellus bat ...	638	638	99%	9e-179	96.62%	387	KX285200.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5 PREDICT-EHA-156-12-NL13849 RNA-dependent RNA polymerase mRNA...	Pipistrellus bat ...	632	632	99%	4e-177	96.35%	387	KX285199.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5 isolate BY140576 RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (RdRp) gene, partial cds	Pipistrellus bat ...	616	616	99%	4e-172	95.57%	406	MN312687.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5 PREDICT-EHA-156-12-NL13847 RNA-dependent RNA polymerase mRNA...	Pipistrellus bat ...	610	610	99%	2e-170	95.32%	387	KX285197.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Bat coronavirus (BtCoV/359A/2005) RNA-dependent RNA polymerase gene, partial cds	Bat coronavirus...	610	610	99%	2e-170	95.31%	437	DQ648810.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Bat coronavirus (BtCoV/A906/2005) RNA-dependent RNA polymerase gene, partial cds	Bat coronavirus...	606	606	99%	3e-169	95.05%	432	DQ648846.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5 isolate_33R RNA-dependent RNA polymerase gene, partial cds	Pipistrellus bat ...	604	604	99%	9e-169	95.06%	2801	KC522089.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5 isolate_26R RNA-dependent RNA polymerase gene, partial cds	Pipistrellus bat ...	604	604	99%	9e-169	95.06%	2801	KC522083.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5 isolate_17R RNA-dependent RNA polymerase gene, partial cds	Pipistrellus bat ...	604	604	99%	9e-169	95.06%	2801	KC522076.1

Supp. Fig. 3. BLAST analysis of the newly discovered Merbecovirus RdRp region against available partial RdRp sequences on GenBank.

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Job Title lcl|NovelMerbecovirusSpike

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Program BLASTN [Citation](#) ▼

Database nt [See details](#) ▼

Query ID lcl|Query_31777

Description lcl|NovelMerbecovirusSpike

Molecule type dna

Query Length 4080

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Percent Identity to **E value** to **Query Coverage** to

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	Description	Common Name	Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E value	Per. Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5 isolate 31S spike glycoprotein gene complete cds	Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5	4950	4950	100%	0.0	88.67%	4065	KC522102.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5 isolate 19S spike glycoprotein gene complete cds	Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5	4909	4909	100%	0.0	88.50%	4062	KC522093.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5 isolate 33S spike glycoprotein gene complete cds	Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5	4848	4848	100%	0.0	88.17%	4080	KC522104.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5 isolate 20S spike glycoprotein gene complete cds	Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5	4789	4789	100%	0.0	87.93%	4077	KC522094.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5 isolate YD13403 complete genome	Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5	4782	4782	100%	0.0	87.92%	30529	MH002342.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5 isolate 18S spike glycoprotein gene complete cds	Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5	4778	4778	100%	0.0	87.88%	4077	KC522092.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pipistrellus abramus bat coronavirus HKU5-related isolate BY140568 complete genome	Pipistrellus abramus bat coronav...	4776	4776	100%	0.0	87.84%	30511	MN611520.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Bat coronavirus HKU5-2 complete genome	Bat coronavirus HKU5-2	4765	4765	100%	0.0	87.82%	30488	EF065510.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Bat coronavirus HKU5-5 complete genome	Bat coronavirus HKU5-5	4759	4759	100%	0.0	87.80%	30487	EF065512.1

Supp. Fig. 4. BLAST hits of the Spike glycoprotein gene of the novel HKU5-related *Merbecovirus*.

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> select all 100 sequences selected		GenPept	Graphics	Distance tree of results	Multiple alignment			
Description	Common Name	Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E value	Per. Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> spike glycoprotein [Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5]	Pipistrellus ba...	2597	2597	99%	0.0	91.11%	1359	AGP04943.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> spike glycoprotein [Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5]	Pipistrellus ba...	2580	2580	99%	0.0	90.37%	1358	AGP04931.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> spike glycoprotein [Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5]	Pipistrellus ba...	2578	2578	99%	0.0	90.37%	1358	AGP04933.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> spike glycoprotein [Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5]	Pipistrellus ba...	2570	2570	99%	0.0	90.30%	1354	AGP04941.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> spike glycoprotein [Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5]	Pipistrellus ba...	2565	2565	99%	0.0	90.52%	1353	AGP04932.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> spike glycoprotein [Pipistrellus abramus bat coronavirus HKU5-related]	Pipistrellus ab...	2561	2561	99%	0.0	90.15%	1359	QHA24687.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> S protein [Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5]	Pipistrellus ba...	2560	2560	99%	0.0	90.23%	1359	AWH65910.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Spike glycoprotein [Bat coronavirus HKU5-2]	Bat coronaviru...	2557	2557	99%	0.0	90.30%	1357	ABN10884.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Spike glycoprotein [Bat coronavirus HKU5-3]	Bat coronaviru...	2556	2556	99%	0.0	90.23%	1357	ABN10893.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> S protein [Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5]	Pipistrellus ba...	2545	2545	99%	0.0	89.64%	1355	AWH65932.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> spike glycoprotein [BfPα-BetaCoV/GD2013]	BfPα-BetaCoV...	2535	2535	99%	0.0	89.57%	1353	AI62343.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> spike glycoprotein [Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5]	Pipistrellus ba...	2531	2531	99%	0.0	89.27%	1353	AGP04942.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> spike glycoprotein [Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5]	Pipistrellus ba...	2526	2526	99%	0.0	89.27%	1353	AGP04935.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> spike glycoprotein [Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5]	Pipistrellus ba...	2524	2524	99%	0.0	89.27%	1353	AGP04934.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> spike glycoprotein [Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5]	Pipistrellus ba...	2523	2523	99%	0.0	88.54%	1357	AGP04937.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> spike glycoprotein [Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5]	Pipistrellus ba...	2521	2521	99%	0.0	88.83%	1353	AGP04940.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> spike glycoprotein [Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5]	Pipistrellus ba...	2521	2521	99%	0.0	88.46%	1357	AGP04938.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> spike glycoprotein [Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5]	Pipistrellus ba...	2521	2521	99%	0.0	88.46%	1357	AGP04939.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> spike glycoprotein [Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5]	Pipistrellus ba...	2513	2513	99%	0.0	88.76%	1352	YP_001039962.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> S protein [Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5]	Pipistrellus ba...	2512	2512	99%	0.0	88.68%	1353	AWH65921.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> spike glycoprotein [Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5]	Pipistrellus ba...	2507	2507	99%	0.0	88.39%	1352	AGP04929.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> spike [Bat coronavirus (BtCoV/A434/2005)]	Bat coronaviru...	2450	2450	96%	0.0	89.14%	1319	ABG11962.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> spike glycoprotein [Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5]	Pipistrellus ba...	2434	2434	99%	0.0	85.53%	1357	AGP04936.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> spike glycoprotein [Pipistrellus bat coronavirus HKU5]	Pipistrellus ba...	2424	2424	99%	0.0	85.89%	1358	AGP04930.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> spike protein [Middle East respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus]	Middle East re...	2049	2049	99%	0.0	72.57%	1345	AUM60024.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> spike protein [Middle East respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus]	Middle East re...	2042	2042	99%	0.0	72.62%	1345	AUM60014.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> spike glycoprotein [BfVs-BetaCoV/SC2013]	BfVs-BetaCoV...	1989	1989	97%	0.0	72.35%	1322	AHY61337.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> S protein [Middle East respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus]	Middle East re...	1981	1981	98%	0.0	70.52%	1347	AWH65954.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> spike glycoprotein [Hypsugo bat coronavirus HKU25]	Hypsugo bat c...	1980	1980	98%	0.0	70.50%	1346	ASL68941.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> S protein [Middle East respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus]	Middle East re...	1974	1974	98%	0.0	70.22%	1346	AWH65943.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> S protein [Middle East respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus]	Middle East re...	1967	1967	99%	0.0	69.56%	1349	AVV62537.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> spike glycoprotein [Hypsugo bat coronavirus HKU25]	Hypsugo bat c...	1964	1964	98%	0.0	70.30%	1346	ASL68953.1

Supp. Fig. 5. BLAST result of spike glycoprotein amino acid sequence against the GenBank nr database confirms its close relationship to Pipistrellus bat Coronavirus HKU5.

Supp. Fig. 6. Multiple sequence alignment of the Spike glycoprotein of the novel HKU5-r CoV (labelled 'Cotton') against other Merbecoviruses plotted using

MultAlin (Corpet, 1988).

>gnl|SRA|SRR5885860.439770805.1 439770805 (Biological)
 CCGACTTTAATCGTTGAACAAACGAACCTTTAATAGCGGCTGCACCATTTGGGGTGTCTTG
 ATCCAACATCGAGGTCGTAACCCATTTGTCGATATGGACTTTGAATAGGATTCGCGT
 TTATCCCTAGG

>gnl|SRA|SRR5885860.439770805.2 439770805 (Biological)
 CCTAGGGATTAACAGCGCAATCCATTTCAAGAGTCCATATCGCAATAAGGGTTTACGACCT
 CGATGTTGGATCAGGACACCCCAATGGTGCAGCCGCTATTAAGGTTCTGTTTGTCAAG
 ATTAAGTCCG

select all 100 sequences selected

Description	Common Name	Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E value	Per. Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Camelus dromedarius isolate camel200 mitochondrion complete genome	Arabian camel	241	241	99%	8e-60	100.00%	16573	MH110007.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Camelus dromedarius isolate camel199 mitochondrion complete genome	Arabian camel	241	241	99%	8e-60	100.00%	16574	MH110006.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Camelus dromedarius isolate camel198 mitochondrion complete genome	Arabian camel	241	241	99%	8e-60	100.00%	16584	MH110005.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Camelus dromedarius isolate camel196 mitochondrion complete genome	Arabian camel	241	241	99%	8e-60	100.00%	16571	MH110004.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Camelus dromedarius isolate camel195 mitochondrion complete genome	Arabian camel	241	241	99%	8e-60	100.00%	16575	MH110003.1

>gnl|SRA|SRR5885859.281856399.1 281856399 (Biological)
 GAGGAATAGTGTAAAGGAGTATGGGGTAATTATGGTGGGCCATACGGTAGTATTTAGTTG
 GGCATTTCACTGTAAAGAGGTGTGGTCTCTTAATCTTTAACTTAAAGGTTAATGCT
 AAGTAGCTTTACAGTGGCTCTAGAGGGG

>gnl|SRA|SRR5885859.281856399.2 281856399 (Biological)
 TAGGGCCGCTATTTACCCTATAGCACCCCTCTACCCCTCTAGAGCCACTGTAAAGCT
 AACTTAGCATTAACCTTTTAAGTTAAGATTAAGAGAACCAACACCTCTTACAGTGAAA
 TGCCCACTAAATACTACCGTAT

select all 100 sequences selected

Description	Common Name	Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E value	Per. Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Homo sapiens isolate VIS5 mitochondrion complete genome	human	278	278	100%	8e-71	100.00%	16564	MT742594.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Homo sapiens isolate VIS4 mitochondrion complete genome	human	278	278	100%	8e-71	100.00%	16564	MT742593.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Homo sapiens isolate VIS3 mitochondrion complete genome	human	278	278	100%	8e-71	100.00%	16560	MT742592.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Homo sapiens isolate UB3 mitochondrion complete genome	human	278	278	100%	8e-71	100.00%	16567	MT742591.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Homo sapiens isolate TE03 mitochondrion complete genome	human	278	278	100%	8e-71	100.00%	16568	MT742590.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Homo sapiens isolate TE013 mitochondrion complete genome	human	278	278	100%	8e-71	100.00%	16560	MT742589.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Homo sapiens isolate A275 mitochondrion complete genome	human	278	278	100%	8e-71	100.00%	16560	MT742587.1

>gnl|SRA|SRR5885860.454079979.1 454079979 (Biological)
 CCGGGTGTCCACCTCTATACCCTACTGTAACATGTGGTGGGCTCATACAATAAACCCCTA
 GGAATCCGATTGATATTAAGCTCACACTATCCATATTAACCAAGGGTCTTTTTTTC
 CTGAGTAATAAGTAACAATATGTGAGATAAT

>gnl|SRA|SRR5885860.454079979.2 454079979 (Biological)
 CCTTTTACTGTCACTACCTGTATTAGCTGCAGGCATTCAATATTGCTAACAGACCGAAA
 TTTAAACACACCTTTTTTACCCCTGCCGAGGGGGGACCCATTCTATATCAACACTT
 GTTTTGTATTCGCTCACCCAGAGGTTTAT

select all 100 sequences selected

Description	Common Name	Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E value	Per. Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pipistrellus abramus mitochondrion complete genome	Pipistrellus ab...	279	279	100%	2e-71	100.00%	17236	KX355640.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pipistrellus abramus mitochondrial DNA complete genome	Pipistrellus ab...	279	279	100%	2e-71	100.00%	16976	AB061528.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pipistrellus abramus voucher ZMMU S-182128 cytochrome oxidase subunit 1 (COI) gene, partial cds; mitoc...	Pipistrellus ab...	207	207	82%	1e-49	96.77%	657	JF444014.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pipistrellus abramus voucher ROM 107567 cytochrome oxidase subunit 1 (COI) gene, partial cds; mitochon...	Pipistrellus ab...	207	207	82%	1e-49	96.77%	656	JF444011.1

Supp. Fig. 7. presence of human, camel and bat mitochondrial DNA sequences in SRR5885860

Supp. Fig. 8. NC_001407.1 read coverage in 3 pooled SRA's from bioproject PRJNA396502.

Supp. Fig. 9. NC_029853.1 read coverage in 3 pooled SRA's from bioproject PRJNA396502.

Supp. Fig. 10. NC_043404.1 read coverage in 3 pooled SRA's from bioproject PRJNA396502.

Target deep sequencing analysis the on- and off-target mutation of BE3 in cotton (SRR7896912)

Supp. Fig. 11. NCBI STAT analysis result for dataset SRR7896912 showing presence of HKU5-r CoV reads.

Target deep sequencing analysis the on- and off-target mutation of BE3 in cotton (SRR7896912) Distribution of the top 397 Blast Hits on 397 subject sequences

Supp. Fig. 12. The HKU5-related Merbecovirus sequences obtained from SRR7896912.

Supp. Fig. 13. BWA MEM alignment of SRR7896912 to MN611520.1 displayed in IGV.

Contig #	Accession number of the most similar sequence	Coverage	Identity
>lcl Query_58903 k141_426 flag=1 multi=8.0000 len=948	MN611520.1	99%	99.26%
>lcl Query_59464 k141_438 flag=1 multi=4.0000 len=556	MN611520.1	100%	100%
>lcl Query_59243 k141_636 flag=1 multi=21.0000 len=472	MN611520.1	100%	97.46%
>lcl Query_59109 k141_237 flag=1 multi=5.0000 len=438	MN611520.1	100%	97.03%
>lcl Query_59080 k141_44 flag=1 multi=13.0000 len=351	MN611520.1	100%	99.72%
>lcl Query_59156 k141_524 flag=1 multi=17.0000	MN611520.1	100%	100%

len=314			
>lcl Query_59093 k141_415 flag=1 multi=9.0000 len=313	MN611520.1	100%	100%

Supp. Table 1: Similarity of HKU5-related Merbecovirus Contig sequences in SRR7896912 to the most similar sequence(s) on the NCBI nr/nt database

Supp. Fig. 14. BLAST result of query of NC_005436.1 against the SRX4734343 experiment in BioProject PRJNA380842.

Sequence	Name of Organism	Accession number	Coverage	Identity
Contig1	Sus Scrofa	MH603005.1	94%	97.32%

Contig2	Sus Scrofa	MF183225. 1	91%	99.49%
Contig3	Sus Scrofa	MH603005. 1	94%	100.00 %
Contig4	Sus Scrofa	MT253545. 1	92%	99.58%
Contig5	Sus Scrofa	MH603005. 1	76%	96.55%
gnl SRA SRR7896912.4284789 .2 4284789	Sus Scrofa	MH603005. 1	86%	100%
gnl SRA SRR7896912.3672026 .2 3672026	Sus Scrofa	FJ236992.1	96%	96.58%
gnl SRA SRR7896916.3854156 .1 3854156	Sus Scrofa	MH603005. 1	94%	90.78%
gnl SRA SRR7896912.2112018 .1 2112018	Sus Scrofa	MH603005. 1	100%	100%
gnl SRA SRR7896912.1075594 .1 1075594	Camelus Dromedariu s	KU605078. 1	100%	97.96%
gnl SRA SRR7896912.4037434 .1 4037434	Sus Scrofa	MH603005. 1	100%	89.33%
gnl SRA SRR7896912.1702921 .2 1702921	Sus Scrofa	MT253545. 1	97%	100%

Supp. Table 2: Similarity and identity of the 12 Mitochondrion-related sequences identified and assembled from SRR7896912 to the closest related sequence on the NCBI nr/nt database

Target deep sequencing analysis the on- and off-target mutation of BE3 in cotton (SRR7896916)

Metadata Analysis Reads Data access **A**

Taxonomy Analysis

Unidentified reads: 1.16%
 Identified reads: 98.84%
 cellular organisms: 98.84%
 Eukaryota: 98.82%
 Viridiplantae: 98.82%
 Gossypium: 98.75%
 Gossypium hirsutum: 50.67%
 Opisthokonta: < 0.01% (47 Kbp)
 Archaea: 0.01%
 Bacteria: < 0.01% (114 Kbp)
 Viruses: < 0.01% (16 Kbp)
 Japanese encephalitis virus: < 0.01% (16 Kbp)

Job Title: MN639770:Japanese encephalitis virus isolate...
 RID: 254F54S001R Search expires on 02-10 20:45 pm Download All
 Program: BLASTN Citation
 Database: SRA See details

SRA Blast search set information
 SRX4734343 SRR7896912 SRR7896916 SRR7896926 SRR7896936

Query Length: 10988
 Other reports: Distance tree of results MSA viewer

Filter Results
 Percent Identity: [] to []
 E value: [] to []
 Query Coverage: [] to []
 Filter Reset

B

Descriptions **Graphic Summary** Alignments

hover to see the title click to show alignments Alignment Scores: < 40 40 - 50 50 - 80 80 - 200 >= 200

121 sequences selected

Distribution of the top 125 Blast Hits on 121 subject sequences

Descriptions **Graphic Summary** Alignments

Sequences producing significant alignments Download Manage columns Show 5000

select all 121 sequences selected Graphics Distance tree of results MSA Viewer

Description	Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E value	Per Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
SRX4734343	273	273	1%	9e-70	100.00%	151	SRA-SRR7896916.7546589.2
SRX4734343	273	273	1%	9e-70	100.00%	151	SRA-SRR7896916.5991984.2
SRX4734343	273	273	1%	9e-70	100.00%	151	SRA-SRR7896916.2887220.1
SRX4734343	273	273	1%	9e-70	100.00%	151	SRA-SRR7896916.2147983.2
SRX4734343	273	273	1%	9e-70	100.00%	151	SRA-SRR7896916.1920030.1
SRX4734343	273	273	1%	9e-70	100.00%	151	SRA-SRR7896916.1919958.1
SRX4734343	273	273	1%	9e-70	100.00%	151	SRA-SRR7896916.631087.2
SRX4734343	269	269	1%	1e-68	100.00%	149	SRA-SRR7896916.7494003.2
SRX4734343	269	269	1%	1e-68	100.00%	149	SRA-SRR7896916.6744042.2

Supp. Fig. 15. A: NCBI STAT analysis result of SRR7896916, showing 16Kbp of sequences identified as “japanese encephalitis virus”. B: 121 sequences from SRR7896916 are mapped to the closest complete genome of the virus, MN639770.

Sequence	Accession Number of the Closest matched sequence	Query Coverage	Pair Identity
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Contig1	MN639770.1	100%	99.42%
Contig2	MN639770.1	95%	99.72%
Contig3	MN639770.1	91%	100%
Contig4	MN639770.1	85%	99.45%
Contig5	MN639770.1	91%	100%
Contig6	MN639770.1	99%	99.06%
Contig7	MN639770.1	86%	99.59%
Contig8	MN639770.1	90%	99.47%
Contig9	MK585066.1	93%	99.04%
Contig10	MN639770.1	88%	99.65%
Contig11	MN639770.1	91%	99.48%
Contig12	MN639770.1	88%	100%
Contig13	MN639770.1	93%	99.09%
Contig14	MN639770.1	82%	99.42%
Contig15	MN639770.1	91%	97.13%
Contig16	MN639770.1	100%	98.02%
Contig17	MN639770.1	88%	93.33%
Contig18	MN639770.1	77%	99.57%
Contig19	MN639770.1	90%	99.50%

Supp. Table 3. mapping of the 19 Contigs related to Japanese Encephalitis Virus obtained from SRR7896916.

Supp. Fig. 16. Bowtie2 alignment of SRR7896916 to MN639770.1, displayed in IGV.

Supp. Fig. 17. Bowtie2 alignment of SRR7896926 to NC_033138.1, displayed in IGV.

Supp. Fig. 18. BLAST search result of HKU4-containing contig sequence against the NCBI nr/nt database.

Supp. Fig. 20. Linear sequence map from the longest single contig from coronaSPAdes assembly with homology to BtTp-BetaCoV/GX2012 extracted from SRR10915173 displayed in SnapGene. Note CMV promoter before the 5' end.

Supp. Fig. 21. Linear sequence map from the second-longest single contig from coronaSPAdes assembly with homology to BtTp-BetaCoV/GX2012 extracted from SRR10915173 displayed in SnapGene.

Supp. Fig. 22. Linear sequence map from the single contig from SPAdes assembly with homology to BtTp-BetaCoV/GX2012 extracted from SRR10915173 displayed in SnapGene.

Supp. Fig. 25. Raw read coverage depth of the largest contig from SPAdes assembly with homology to BtTp-BetaCoV/GX2012 displayed in IGV.

Supp. Fig. 26: BLAST search of the HKU4-containing Contig sequence against the NCBI nr/nt database revealed that it is only 98.38% similar to the closest known sequence of HKU4, BtTp-BetaCoV/GX2012.

Supp. Fig. 28. Raw reads for eight pooled sequence read datasets from PRJNA358135 aligned to KF367457.1

Supp. Fig. 29. Contig k79_26763 from de novo assembly of eight pooled sequence read datasets from PRJNA358135 plotted in addgene.

Supp. Fig. 30. SARS CoV WIV1 N protein match. blastx result of match to nr database for ORF identified in contig k79_26763 (403nt to 1661nt) from de novo assembly of eight pooled sequence read datasets from PRJNA358135.

Supp. Fig. 31. Contig k79_969 from de novo assembly of SRR7896912 from PRJNA380842 plotted in addgene.

Contigs

13 HKU5 Contigs assembled from SRR5885860

>Contig1

CCTATCCAGCTTCTGACTTGCCTTATAGCCTCCTCACGTGTAATGAAGAGTT
 TTGGGTAG

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GTCAAGCCC
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9 HKU5 Contigs assembled from SRR7896912

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12 Mitochondria-related sequences obtained from SRR7896912

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18 Hepatitis C virus-related reads observed in SRR10751664

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121 sequences related to Japanese Encephalitis Virus in SRR7896916

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19 Contig sequences assembled from the 121 sequences mapped to Japanese Encephalitis Virus in SRR7896916

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>Contig2

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>Contig3

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>Contig5

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>Contig6

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>Contig9

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>Contig19

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